

TIPS ON HOW TO TEACH TRAGEDY “Romeo and Juliet” by W.Shakespeare

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Abordarea comunicativă este pe larg folosită în învățarea unei limbi străine. Mai jos vom prezenta un proiect de lecție pentru predarea unei tragedii la orele de limbă engleză, și anume a tragediei “Romeo și Julieta” de W.Shakespeare. “Romeo și Julieta” este o tragedie scrisă de William Shakespeare despre soarta a doi îndrăgostiți care luptă împotriva prejudecăților sociale, a urii între familii, a ambiției vanitoase și a destinului. Tragedia celor doi adolescenți, fatal îndrăgostiți unul de altul este probabil cea mai cunoscută piesă a Bardului, unul dintre succesele sale timpurii, fiind considerată cea mai tipică poveste de dragoste a Renașterii. Proiectul dat are o valoare practică și poate fi utilizat pe larg la ore cu studenții cu nivelul de cunoaștere a limbii B1-B2.

Cuvinte-cheie: tragedie, proiect didactic, competență, cunoaștere, aplicare, integrare.

Lesson Plan

Date _____	Level: intermediate
Group _____	Skills: reading, writing, speaking and listening
Speciality _____	Time required: 12 hours (6 periods)
Faculty _____	Topic: “Romeo and Juliet” by W.Shakespeare
University Moldova	
State University	

Materials needed:

- handouts
- chalk and chalkboard
- a laptop computer
- projector and projector screen

Classroom interactions: individual work, pair work, discussions involving the entire class.

Objectives:

- to read and discuss the tragedy “Romeo and Juliet” by W. Shakespeare;
- to define the genre of DRAMA and its sub-genres;
- to identify the 9 elements of Shakespearean tragedy;
- to enrich students’ vocabulary;
- to write the plot summary of the tragedy using the Somebody-Wanted-But-So-Then Strategy;
- to analyze the characters from the tragedy;
- to reflect and analyze the themes and values of “Romeo and Juliet”;
- to analyze the symbols and motifs;
- to develop students’ critical thinking;
- to provide practice and feedback from the students.

Procedures	Aims	Contents
Introduction	Stating the lesson objectives and the new topic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Welcome the class and present the topic and the objectives - Announce the subject of the lesson: Topic: “Romeo and Juliet” by W. Shakespeare
Development of the lesson Pre-Reading	Brainstorming Tapping background knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The quotation of the lesson: “With Love and Patience, Nothing is Impossible.” (Daisaku Ikeda – Japanese writer). Ask students to comment on it. - Ask students to give their own definition of LOVE.

	<u>Handouts</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Give students handouts with information about the 3 genres of literature. - Ask students to explain what the characteristics/specific features of a tragedy are. - <i>traces the rise and fall of a tragic hero with a tragic flaw;</i> - <i>includes conflict, suffering, and catharsis;</i> - <i>can contain elements of tragedy (tragicomedy).</i> - Give students handouts with the 9 Elements of Shakespearean Tragedy. - <i>tragic hero, a struggle between good and evil, hamartia, tragic waste, external conflict, internal conflict, catharsis, supernatural elements, lack of poetic justice, comic relief.</i>
	Author <u>Handouts</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Give students handouts with some information about William Shakespeare.
	Plot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ask students to read the transcripts for “Romeo and Juliet”.
Under- standing	Vocabulary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ask students to match the vocabulary with the correct definitions and write a-h next to the numbers 1-8.
	Reordering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>1b, 2e, 3a, 4g, 5c, 6h, 7d, 8f</i> - Ask students to put the events from the tragedy in the correct order.
	Multiple Choice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>3, 6, 5, 2, 4, 1, 7</i> - Ask students to choose the correct option to complete the sentences.

	Summary	<p>- <i>1b, 2a, 3c, 4a, 5c, 6c, 7a, 8b, 9a, 10c, 11b, 12a</i></p> <p>Ask students to write the summary of “Romeo and Juliet” according to the <i>Somebody-Wanted-But-So-Then</i> Strategy.</p> <p><i>Romeo and Juliet fall in love at a party. But they come from families which hate each other. They are sure they will not be allowed to marry. Nevertheless, helped by Friar Laurence, they marry in secret instead. Unfortunately, before their wedding night Romeo kills Juliet’s cousin in a duel, and in the morning, he is forced to leave her. If he ever returns to the city, he will be put to death.</i></p> <p><i>Juliet’s parents told her she must marry Paris. Her parents do not know she is already married. She refuses in the beginning, but later agrees because she plans to fake her death and escape to be with Romeo forever; again with the help of Friar Laurence.</i></p> <p><i>Friar Laurence designs the plan. He gives Juliet a sleeping potion. She appears to be dead and was put in a tomb. However, Romeo does not know about the plan, visits her grave, thinks she is dead, and kills himself. When Juliet finally wakes up, she discovers that Romeo is dead and then kills herself.</i></p>
	Themes Values	<p>- Ask students to analyze the themes and values of “Romeo and Juliet”.</p> <p>- <i>Love, passion and violence, fate and chance, duality of light and dark, time</i></p> <p>- <i>Marriage, loyalty. Friendship</i></p>

	Characters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ask students to analyze the main characters in “Romeo and Juliet”. - <i>Romeo, Julio, Friar Lawrence, Paris, Tybalt, Capulet, etc.</i>
	Symbols	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ask students to analyze symbols in “Romeo and Juliet”. - <i>Poison, rose, fire, stars, masks.</i>
	Motifs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ask students to analyze the motifs in “Romeo and Juliet”. - <i>Life and death, love and hate, dark and light, Montagues and Capulets, high and low, peace and fighting, young and old.</i>
Assessment/ Hometask	<i>Writing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ask students to choose one of the lessons taken from “Romeo and Juliet” and comment on it. <i>a) Love is blind.</i> <i>b) Love brings out the best in us.</i> <i>c) Life without love is not worth living.</i> <i>d) Love stories don’t always end happily.</i> <i>e) But in the end, love is still stronger than hate.</i>

Handouts for students

DRAMA

Drama is a literary work written to be performed in front of an audience. It contains dialogue, and actors impersonate the characters. It is usually divided into acts or scenes, and relies on props or imaginative dialogue to create a visual experience for the audience.

Primary Sub-Genres of Drama

- Comedy
- History
- Melodrama
- Musical
- **Tragedy**

Preparation

Match the vocabulary with the correct definition and write a–h next to the numbers 1–8.

- | | |
|-----------------------------|--|
| 1. to take place | a. to really want something |
| 2. to step in | b. to happen |
| 3. to be keen for something | c. wearing different clothes so that people don't know who you are |
| 4. lifeless | d. a minister of the church who performs ceremonies, like marriage |
| 5. in disguise | e. to get involved |
| 6. poison | f. a space under the ground or inside a stone building to bury a dead person |
| 7. a priest | g. dead |
| 8. a tomb | h. a substance that causes illness or death |

1. Check your understanding: reordering

Write a number (1–7) to put these events from the tragedy in order.

- _____ Romeo and Juliet secretly get married.
- _____ Juliet wakes up, sees Romeo and kills herself.
- _____ Romeo thinks Juliet is really dead. He takes poison.
- _____ Romeo and Juliet meet and fall in love.
- _____ Juliet takes a drug to make people think she's dead.
- _____ The Montagues and the Capulets hate each other.
- _____ The two families make peace.

2. Check your understanding: multiple choice

Choose the correct option to complete the sentence.

1. The Montagues and the Capulets hate each other so much that they ...

- a) don't speak to each other.
- b) fight whenever they meet.
- c) play horrible tricks on each other.

2. The Capulets organize a party to ...

- a) introduce their daughter to a possible husband.
- b) introduce Juliet to the Montagues.
- c) celebrate Juliet's fourteenth birthday.

3. Romeo and his friends...

- a) watch the party from a safe distance.
- b) plan to cause trouble at the party.
- c) go to the party in disguise.

4. When Romeo and Juliet meet...

- a) they fall in love immediately.
- b) they don't like each other at first.
- c) Juliet doesn't feel the same way as Romeo.

5. Romeo and Juliet go to a priest called Friar Lawrence to...

- a) get advice.
- b) ask him to persuade their families to make peace.
- c) get married.

6. Romeo kills Tybalt because...

- a) Tybalt wants to stop him seeing Juliet.
- b) Tybalt is planning to kill Romeo.
- c) Tybalt kills Romeo's best friend.

7. Juliet's parents are angry because...

- a) she won't marry Count Paris.
- b) they think she is too friendly with the Montague family.
- c) they find out about the secret wedding.

8. Friar Lawrence says he will help Juliet by...

- a) helping her to escape with Romeo.
- b) giving her a drug to make people think she is dead.
- c) talking to her parents.

9. The plan goes wrong because...

- a) Romeo doesn't get Friar Lawrence's message.
- b) the drug is too strong.
- c) Juliet's family don't believe that she is dead.

10. Romeo drinks poison because...

- a) he thinks Juliet doesn't love him.
- b) he knows he has brought shame on his family.
- c) he thinks Juliet is dead.

11. When Juliet wakes up...

- a) she realizes she's trapped in the tomb.
- b) she commits suicide.
- c) she shouts for help.

12. In the end, the Montagues and the Capulets...

- a) are united by their loss and make peace.
- b) continue fighting until they are all dead.
- c) think the tragedy is Friar Lawrence's fault.

3. Write the summary of "Romeo and Juliet".

4. Analyze the themes and values of "Romeo and Juliet".

5. Analyze the main characters.

Discussion

Are Romeo and Juliet's deaths just a tragic accident? If not, who is responsible?

Do you think the story of Romeo and Juliet is relevant to life today?

6. Analyze the symbols in "Romeo and Juliet".

A symbol is something that stands for more than itself...*symbols in Romeo and Juliet include poison, roses, fire, stars, and masks.*

7. Analyze the motifs in "Romeo and Juliet".

8. Choose one of the lessons taken from "Romeo and Juliet" and comment on it in writing in about 200-250 words.

- a) Love is blind.
- b) Love brings out the best in us.
- c) Life without love is not worth living.
- d) Love stories don't always end happily.
- e) But in the end, love is still stronger than hate.

References:

- 1. <http://listentogenius.com/recordings/TheLastLeaf.mp3>
- 2. <http://www.eastoftheweb.com/short-stories/UBooks/LasLea.shtml>
- 3. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1dhs1pHyGOI>